

Lion Temple (Apedemak Temple) at Musawwarat es-Sufra

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Entry tags: Monument, Archaeological monument, Religious Group, Meroitic religion, Religious Place, Temple

The Lion Temple (or Apedemak Temple) at Musawwarat es-Sufra is a typical Meroitic single-roomed temple, dedicated to the lion god Apedemak, an indigenous Meroitic deity. It was constructed under king Arnakhamani (c. 235–218 BC) and is one of the most important religious monuments of the Early Meroitic period, testifying to seminal changes in Kushite religion in the 4th and 3rd centuries BC. In the previous Napatan period (c. 650–300 BC), the Kushite pantheon – at least as represented in monumental sources – is exclusively composed of gods with an origin in Pharaonic Egypt, such as Amun. Non-Egyptian indigenous deities only appear in the subsequent Meroitic period (c. 300 BC–350 AD). The Lion Temple at Musawwarat is a manifestation of this development: The gods Apedemak, Sebiuameker and Arensnuphis are depicted here for the first time.

Date Range: 235 BCE - 300 CE

Region: Musawwarat es-Sufra

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Sudan, Keraba, Musawwarat es-Sufra

This entry focuses on the Lion Temple at Musawwarat es-Sufra, an archaeological site in present-day Sudan. Musawwarat es-Sufra is situated about 180 km northeast of Sudan's modern capital Khartoum, 25 km outside of the Nile valley in the semiarid landscape of the Keraba.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hintze, Fritz 1962. Die Inschriften des Löwentempels von Musawwarat es Sufra. Abhandlungen der Deutschen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin. Klasse für Sprachen, Literatur und Kunst. Berlin: Akademie Verlag.
- Source 2: Hintze, Fritz (ed.) 1971. Musawwarat es Sufra 1,2. Der Löwentempel, Tafelband. Berlin: Akademie Verlag.
- Source 3: Hintze, Fritz (ed.) 1993. Musawwarat es Sufra 1,1. Der Löwentempel, Textband. Berlin: Akademie Verlag.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://zamaniproject.org/site-sudan-Musawwarat-es-Sufra.html#header7-b2>

– Source 1 Description: 3D model of the Lion Temple.

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.musawwarat.com/>

– Source 2 Description: Introductory information on the archaeological site of Musawwarat es-Sufra and its main monuments.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: The Lion Temple of Musawwarat had already collapsed in antiquity, shortly after its construction, due to insufficient foundations. In the 1960s the site was excavated and many of the decorated sandstone blocks of the temple were found in an exceptionally good condition, untouched by wind and sand abrasion. As a result, the temple could be completely re-erected. It received a modern roof and was finally inaugurated in 1970. The roof was renewed in 2015. The temple had been surrounded by a large oval enclosure with an entrance in the southeast in antiquity. The wall visible today at the back of the temple is a modern protective measure to shield the temple from wind and sand abrasion. Its outline does not follow the ancient enclosure wall.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1960-1970, 2015

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Archaeological Mission of Humboldt University Berlin, The Archaeological Mission to Musawwarat

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

– Other [specify]: The Lion Temple at Musawwarat is situated in a wide basin of the Wadi es-Sufra, bordered by sandstone escarpments which rise up to 60 m above the valley floor. A wadi is a valley that periodically turns into a river, channeling the surface run-off of the rain falling in its upper reaches and the surrounding hills during the rainy season and transporting them towards the Nile. In antiquity, as today, the yearly summer rains were the only available source of water in Musawwarat. Today the annual rainfall is about 100 mm. In the first millennium BC it was probably only a little higher, but

interannual fluctuations were lower. Thus, for the Meroitic period the environment of Musawwarat can be pictured as a dry savannah. During the summer rains, the Wadi es-Sufra, which joins the larger Wadi Awateib south of Musawwarat, periodically turns into a rapid stream. Wadis are typical features of the (semi)arid landscapes in the Keraba region.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: Great Hafir, a monumental artificial water reservoir

Notes: By its position, the Lion Temple is connected to the Great Hafir, at the foot of which it is situated. Hafayir (Arabic; sg. hafir) are monumental artificial water reservoirs which were built in the savannah landscapes of Sudan from antiquity (and continue to be built until today). Ancient hafayir in the Keraba are often associated with one-roomed temples of presumably Meroitic date. While it has been assumed for a long time that both, the Lion Temple and the Great Hafir at Musawwarat are of the same age, recent investigations have proved the Great Hafir to be of Napatan date and considerably older than the Lion Temple – which must therefore be understood as a later addition to the assemblage.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: The site of Musawwarat is situated 25 km outside the Nile valley in the semiarid landscape of the Keraba which only supports nomadic ways of life - today as in the Meroitic past. Archaeological evidence for substantial habitation activities at the site is lacking. Findings confirm the overall interpretation of Musawwarat as a primarily sacral site which never sustained a large-scale settled population. While we can assume that nomadic populations frequented the area at all times, none of the archaeological remains can be conclusively attributed to them.

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The Lion Temple is part of an extensive site whose central monument is the so-called Great Enclosure, an architecturally unique assemblage which comprises three temples, partly erected on artificial terraces, connected by ramps, corridors and passages, and surrounded by huge walled courtyards. Other features and monuments are widely distributed over an area of more than 3.5 x 1 km. Intensive surveys and excavations have led to the identification of more than 30 elements. They include: - further small temples and shrines (II A, II B, II D) and a small church (III A) - secular buildings (I C) as well as unclassified buildings (I D, III B 1, III B 2) - habitation sites (I G, I H, II J, III D) - workshop areas (II G) - quarries (I J, I K, III C, III E) - hafayir, i.e. artificial water reservoirs, and water ducts (I N, II F) - cemeteries (I F, I L, II N, III F, IV A) - unclassified features (II K, II L, II M) Only some of these sites and monuments have been explored in detail. Many details concerning the function of some of the features, their chronological position and their association with each other remain to be investigated and understood.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: The entire site of Musawwarat es-Sufra has been interpreted as a pilgrimage centre, based on the architecture of the Great Enclosure which features huge courtyards surrounding three temples, and the absence of evidence for a settled population at the site. The site has been related to the Meroitic lion god Apedemak, to whom also the Lion Temple is dedicated.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The Lion Temple was constructed under king Arnakhamani (c. 235–218 BC). It collapsed at an unknown point in time, shortly after its construction, due to insufficient foundations.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

Notes: The Lion Temple was constructed under king Arnakhamani (c. 235–218 BC). It

collapsed at an unknown point in time, shortly after its construction, due to insufficient foundations.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: The Lion Temple was constructed under king Arnakhamani (c. 235–218 BC). It collapsed at an unknown point in time, shortly after its construction, due to insufficient foundations.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Notes: The front of the temple is designed as a pylon, following Egyptian architectural models. A first pylon (which had been decorated with reliefs) had been taken down already in antiquity, likely because of structural instability. A new, undecorated, pylon was constructed to replace the first one.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The Lion Temple collapsed already in antiquity, shortly after its construction, due to insufficient foundations. In the 1960s it was excavated and many of the decorated sandstone blocks of the temple were found in an exceptionally good condition, untouched by wind and sand abrasion. As a result, the temple could be completely re-erected. It received a modern roof and was finally inaugurated in 1970. The roof was renewed in 2015. The temple had been surrounded by a large oval enclosure with an entrance in the southeast in antiquity. The wall visible today at the back of the temple is a modern protective measure to shield the temple from wind and sand abrasion. Its outline does not follow the ancient enclosure wall.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Lion Temple at Musawwarat is dedicated to the lion god Apedemak, an indigenous Meroitic god.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: One scene of the relief decoration (on one of the columns in the temple's interior) has been interpreted as representing the king in front of a deceased earlier ruler, i.e. potentially an ancestor.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

– Other [specify]: The Lion Temple at Musawwarat was commissioned by the Meroitic king Arnakhamani (c. 235–218 BC). This is evident from the inscriptions and the depictions of Arnakhamani in the relief decoration of the temple.

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We don't know by whom the temple was actually built though we can assume that it was a workforce whose specialist members were brought to the site from the Nile valley.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We have no evidence on the origins of the cult of Apedemak in Musawwarat.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We have no evidence on the origins of the cult of Apedemak in Musawwarat.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We have no evidence on the origins of the cult of Apedemak in Musawwarat.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Unkown.

Notes: We have no evidence on the origins of the cult of Apedemak in Musawwarat and we do not know what prompted the construction of the Lion Temple.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Lion Temple at Musawwarat is a typical Meroitic single-roomed temple with six interior columns supporting the roof construction. The front of the temple is designed as a pylon, following Egyptian architectural models. A first pylon had been taken down already in antiquity, likely because of structural instability. A new pylon was constructed to replace the first one.

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This entry is about a temple, so area equals monument.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 140

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 6.6

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Notes: The walls of the Lion Temple were built of locally quarried sandstone blocks. The roof of the temple had been made of organic materials, i.e. timber and likely matting, in antiquity. None of the latter materials has been preserved.

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A few surviving remains of plaster indicate that the walls of the temple had been plastered in antiquity. It is unknown whether the raw material for the plaster had been sourced locally.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A few surviving remains of plaster indicate that the walls of the temple had been plastered in antiquity. It is unknown whether the raw material for the plaster had been sourced locally.

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The roof of the temple had been made of organic materials, i.e. timber and likely matting, in antiquity. None of the latter materials has been preserved. Given the size the beams needed to have, it is unlikely that they had been fashioned from local savannah trees.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The roof of the temple had been made of organic materials, i.e. timber and likely matting, in antiquity. None of the latter materials has been preserved. Given the size the beams needed to have, it is unlikely that they had been fashioned from local

savannah trees which means that they would have been imported to Musawwarat.

↳ Grass

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The roof of the temple had been made of organic materials, i.e. timber and likely matting, in antiquity. None of the latter materials has been preserved. Thus, the exact nature of the roofing material is unknown.

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The walls of the Lion Temple were built of locally quarried sandstone blocks. Several ancient quarries have been identified in the valley of Musawwarat.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: All outer walls of the temple are decorated in sunk relief. The reliefs on the sidewalls depict king Arnakhamani and a prince, protected by the goddess Isis, venerating a succession of deities – six gods on the southern wall, four divine couples on the northern wall. The back wall shows Arnakhamani venerating the gods Apedemak and Sebiuameker. All representations are accompanied by inscriptions, which give the names of the royal persons and the deities as well as short hymns to the latter. These texts are related to early Ptolemaic Egyptian inscriptions on the temple of Isis on Philae above the First Cataract, the southernmost temple in Egyptian core territory. A sculptured triple protome showing a ram's head as the symbol of the god Amun flanked by two lion heads as the symbol of Apedemak was placed over the entrance. Four drain spouts from the roof were surmounted by a lion protome each.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: All inner walls of the temple as well as the columns were decorated in relief. Their preservation is more fragmentary than the decoration on the outside walls. They comprise complex, small-scaled scenes with a closer relationship to the cult practices in the temple.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Two sandstone statues of seated lions flanked the entrance to the temple.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The reliefs on the outer sidewalls depict king Arnakhamani and a prince, protected by the goddess Isis, venerating a succession of deities – six gods on the southern wall, four divine couples on the northern wall. The back wall shows Arnakhamani venerating the gods Apedemak and Sebiuwerker. All representations are accompanied by inscriptions, which give the names of the royal persons and the deities as well as short hymns to the latter. These texts are related to early Ptolemaic Egyptian inscriptions on the temple of Isis on Philae above the First Cataract, the southernmost temple in Egyptian core territory. All inner walls of the temple as well as the columns were decorated in relief. Their preservation is more fragmentary than the decoration on the outside walls. They comprise complex, small-scaled scenes with a closer relationship to the cult practices in the temple.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The reliefs on the outer sidewalls depict king Arnakhamani and a prince, protected by the goddess Isis, venerating a succession of deities – six gods on the southern wall, four divine couples on the northern wall. The back wall shows Arnakhamani venerating the gods Apedemak and Sebiuwerker. All inner walls of the temple as well as the columns are decorated in relief, comprising complex, small-scaled scenes with a closer relationship to the cult practices in the temple. They

include representations of king Arnakhamani and members of the royal family. A subordinate frieze shows cattle, elephants, lions and human prisoners.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: A subordinate frieze which is part of the decoration of the interior walls of the temple shows lions and rows of cattle and elephants as well as human prisoners.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Decorative elements of Egyptian origin (torus roll, cavetto cornice, uraeus frieze) framed the entrance to the temple.

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: The figural decoration of the temple is accompanied by inscriptions, which give the names of the royal persons and the deities as well as short hymns to the latter. These texts are related to early Ptolemaic Egyptian inscriptions on the temple of Isis on Philae above the First Cataract, the southernmost temple in Egyptian core territory.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: No, the decoration is displayed openly, though we do not know whether the access to the temple had been restricted in antiquity.

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

Notes: A sandstone throne was found inside the temple, in front of the rear wall. It has been interpreted as the pedestal for the cult image (which itself is not preserved). The throne was surrounded by a wooden shrine of which only traces of the foundation were found in the excavations. Next to it, two plates of lead in the shape of bound prisoners were found. Another sandstone stand, probably for a portable shrine or barque was also found inside the temple.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Two sandstone statues of seated lions, symbolizing Apedemak, the deity of the temple, flanked the entrance to the temple. A sculptured triple protome showing a ram's head as the symbol of the god Amun flanked by two lion heads as the symbol of Apedemak was placed over the entrance. Four drain spouts from the roof are surmounted by a lion protome each.

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: The reliefs on the outer sidewalls depict king Arnakhamani and a prince, protected by the goddess Isis, venerating a succession of deities – six gods on the southern wall, four divine couples on the northern wall. The back wall shows Arnakhamani venerating the gods Apedemak and Sebiuwerker. All representations are accompanied by inscriptions, which give the names of the royal persons and the deities as well as short hymns to the latter. These texts are related to early Ptolemaic Egyptian inscriptions on the temple of Isis on Philae above the First Cataract, the southernmost temple in Egyptian core territory. All inner walls of the temple as well as the columns were decorated in relief. Their preservation is more fragmentary than the decoration on the outside walls. They comprise complex, small-scaled scenes with a closer relationship to the cult practices in the temple. Various deities, first and foremost Amun and Apedemak are depicted being venerated by the king and members of the royal family. Representations include offering and greeting scenes.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Decoration of the columns include scenes which have been interpreted mythical scenes depicting sacred animals and plants.

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Among the representations decorating the inside of the temple, two scenes have been interpreted as showing the election and the coronation of the king.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– No

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: All representations are accompanied by inscriptions, which give the names of the royal persons and the deities as well as short hymns to the latter. These texts are related to early Ptolemaic Egyptian inscriptions on the temple of Isis on Philae above the First Cataract, the southernmost temple in Egyptian core territory.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The iconography of the deities depicted is specific to the Meroitic sphere. This goes particularly for Apedemak, but also for the gods Arensnuphis and Sebiemeker.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: The iconography of the king and the prince depicted is specific to the Meroitic sphere. T

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The temple was dedicated to the lion god Apedemak, an indigenous Meroitic god. In previous periods, the pantheon – at least as represented in official sources – is exclusively composed of gods with an origin in Pharaonic Egypt, such as Amun. Non-Egyptian indigenous deities only appear in the subsequent Meroitic period (c. 300 BC–350 AD). The Lion Temple at Musawwarat is a manifestation of this development: The gods Apedemak, Sebiumecker and Arensnuphis are depicted here for the first time.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Apedemak is depicted as lion-headed with a human body.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Archaeologists assume that Musawwarat was place of pilgrimage as no evidence of substantial habitation is present at the site. However, no further details about the nature and the role of the pilgrimages are known or can be inferred from the evidence.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Based on the decoration of the temple which shows the king venerating deities, we can assume that rituals were undertaken at the temple - conducted by the king and/or priests.

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: unknown
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We can only assume that priests undertook the service at the temple and performed the rituals. We have no direct evidence on this aspect.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Josefine Kuckertz undefined. Meroitic temples and their decoration. (Dietrich Raue undefined, Ed.), Handbook of Ancient Nubia. De Gruyter.